

Fouling and scaling in reverse osmosis desalination plants: A critical review of membrane autopsies, feedwater quality guidelines and assessment methods

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Reverse osmosis (RO) is increasingly applied to address water scarcity, but feedwater quality is crucial.
- Operational issues observed in RO plants are discussed through a review of membrane autopsy literature.
- Current and emerging RO feedwater assessment methods and guidelines are critically reviewed.
- Supplier and proposed threshold guidelines of fouling/scaling potentials are discussed.
- Comparison of guidelines with full-scale plant feedwater qualities highlight current limitations.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Reverse osmosis (RO) desalination currently plays a vital role in addressing the critical and growing issue of water scarcity through desalination of brackish waters (BWRO) and seawater (SWRO). To ensure sustainable operation and longer membrane lifetime in an RO system, it is crucial to monitor and evaluate the feedwater quality of the desalination process. This article highlights the operational challenges faced by seawater and brackish water RO desalination plants through a review of full-scale plant membrane autopsies. The operational issues of particulate, colloidal, inorganic, organic, and biological fouling thus highlighted require to be managed and monitored for plants to perform efficiently. The paper then explores the potential and limitations of conventional and novel analytical methods such as modified fouling index (MFI), transparent exopolymer particles (TEP), liquid chromatography-organic carbon detection (LC-OCD), etc. as tools for the understanding and control of these issues. The application of these tools is then studied through a review of available RO feedwater quality which, compared to supplier and literature guidelines, allows to underscore the difficulties of matching these

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guidelines and finding proper control targets and measures for organic, biological, oxidative and inorganic fouling. Finally, the paper discusses an overview of areas of improvement on which to focus future research.

1. Introduction

Issues of water scarcity combined with increasing population in urban and coastal areas have been driving the growth of the desalination market whether for treating seawater, brackish water sources or wastewater. Total global capacity of desalination technology has already exceeded ~ 115 million m^3/day with an additional >60 million m^3/year coming from wastewater reuse applications [1]. Desalination technologies are generally separated into two categories: thermal processes which represented the majority of applications through the mid-90s and membrane-based systems (reverse-osmosis, RO) which took over and have grown exponentially since the early 2000s due to significant improvements in energy reduction [1]. Currently, desalinated water is produced about 80 % by RO and 20 % by thermal processes. While still a critical aspect of these applications, energy consumption has been halved over the last 20 years and the industry's carbon footprint would benefit greatly by an evolution towards the use of renewable energy sources.

As presented in Fig. 1, the main resource used for RO desalination is seawater with a total capacity of ~ 51 Mm^3/d . The three main sectors relying on desalination are: production of drinking water, water for industry (with TDS <10 mg/L), and water for irrigation (see Fig. 1). While the use of brackish water sources is more cost-effective due to lower salinities, only North America uses these in a majority of their applications (Fig. 2). China, Japan, South Korea and Taiwan equally divide their desalination technologies between seawater, brackish and wastewater while Singapore, an important player in this field relative to its population size, applies desalination equally to seawater and wastewater reuse. Despite global growth, the main market remains the Middle East and North African regions which represent 70 % of the installed capacity and where desalination targets mainly drinking water production. This is true overall, with over 75 % of desalination capacity producing drinking water while around 20 % targets industrial demand, mainly in Asia and South America.

While seawater reverse osmosis (SWRO) desalination is now the most common application worldwide, it is not without its specific operational issues to be considered. In particular, membrane fouling and

scaling are the most critical aspects that need monitoring and control [3,4]. The impact of scaling and fouling of RO units results in several negative effects on process performance including the need for frequent chemical cleaning, a decrease in production capacity, increased energy and membrane replacement costs as well as degraded water quality [3,5]. These issues translate in terms of operations in (1) increased pressure differential across the membrane modules causing potential damage to the elements (telescoping, channelling, squeezing), (2) increased membrane resistance requiring higher pressure to maintain production and (3) increased salts passage caused by an accumulation of salts at the surface of the membrane, a process known as concentration polarization.

These operational issues are compounded by the increase in the number of RO plants ($>22,800$ as of 2023) and in particular an ongoing trend towards design of so-called extra-large plants with capacities $>50,000$ m^3/d [1,6] as presented in Fig. 3. Seawater is the feedwater of more than half (157 plants) of these extra-large RO plants, while the rest are desalinating brackish water (35 plants), wastewater (29 plants), river water (16 plants) and pure/tap water (3 plants). These larger plants represent specific technical issues as the required maintenance (e. g., cleaning-in-place type and frequency) is a significant challenge under these conditions [3,6]. It is therefore critical to develop tools to properly monitor feedwater quality and pre-treatment performance to ensure sustainable performance of these plants.

There exists a large amount of literature on the subject of RO desalination and in particular several reviews of the issues and advances of the field in recent years. These include among others the state of the art on desalination technology [7], the environmental impact of these processes [8,9], the issues of energy [10,11], the requirement for pre-treatment ahead of RO membranes [12] and fouling control throughout industrial plants [13–15]. At the same time, studies available on full-scale plants are also available but are rarely the subject of consolidated reviews which we propose in this paper.

The aim of this work is to evaluate the current and future needs for assessment tools and treatment targets in RO desalination of both brackish water and seawater sources through a review of available full-scale plant data. The specific objectives are *i*) to review the extent of

Fig. 1. Growth of global reverse osmosis desalination production capacity per feed water type, and distribution of applications for each feed water type in 2024 (inset bar graph). Produced with information from [2].

issues referenced in the available literature on full-scale plant RO membrane autopsies, *ii*) to discuss the state-of-the-art of tools available for monitoring of fouling issues and water quality, *iii*) to review the current state of RO feedwater quality guidelines and *iv*) to compare them to the available data of full-scale industrial RO desalination plants.

2. RO plant operational issues observed from membrane autopsies

To evaluate the issues plaguing a reverse osmosis unit, it is necessary to complete an autopsy of one or several membranes from the unit in operation. This action requires sacrificing a membrane module as there are no alternatives to accessing information concerning the material fouling the membranes. This represents a critical aspect of RO unit operation and control [16]. Despite this, as noted previously by [17], the majority of membrane autopsy data available in the literature is from lab-scale or pilot studies. Furthermore, available full-scale plant autopsy data is often not combined with RO feedwater chemical and physical characteristics which would be important to assess fouling sources. To try and evaluate the frequency and relative importance of the different fouling issues that plague RO units, a review of available literature on autopsies for both seawater and brackish water full-scale RO plants was completed and is presented in detail in the supplementary information (Table S1). A summarized table of representative studies is presented here (Table 1).

Two comprehensive reviews of autopsies were completed by [18,19]. The latter studied 500 seawater and brackish water autopsies and highlighted that 60 % of these suffered from significant fouling. Both SWRO and BWRO plants showed high levels of biological (40.5 % and 26.3 %, respectively) and colloidal matter fouling (38 % and 24.8 %, respectively). The SWRO membranes then showed a higher propensity for metal (20.3 %) and organic (15.2 %) fouling while BWRO mostly further faced scaling (21.4 %) issues. The study by [18] showed similar data though adding a significant number of oxidative issues observed in SWRO units.

The other SWRO full-scale plant studies reviewed highlight that biological and organic fouling are prevalent in such systems with a more pronounced importance compared to inorganic issues. However, studies from various geographical locations such as Spain, the Middle East and China [27–29] showed that SWRO sites could also be concerned mainly by inorganic scaling. The consolidated BWRO data confirmed that such

units can be challenged by significant biological fouling as evidenced by [19]. Unfortunately, it is generally difficult to conclude as to the reasons for the occurrence of the fouling as the different studies provided very little feedwater quality and operational data. Of the parameters available, feedwater metals concentration appears to be the most at odds with the available guidelines (ASTM, membrane manufacturers, legislation). However, the lack of feedwater quality highlights the need to provide such data, in particular concerning guideline parameters (Table), to provide more insight to the field: operational data (normalised permeability, normalised pressure drop, normalised salt passage, CIP frequency, criteria for CIP, etc.) would also be valuable.

Overall, membrane autopsies, as discussed earlier, are shown to be critical tools in understanding operational issues of full-scale RO plants. It is a particularly relevant tool for investigating the different fouling phenomena and how they appear to develop in the units. They also allow to assess that accumulation of material can be quite significant even when the feedwater quality appears to be under control. Two major drawbacks stand out in light of this: (1) autopsies, due to their destructive nature, cannot be used as a monitoring tool for RO operations and (2) are often provided without a study of the feedwater quality, both on the day of sampling and over the lifetime of the membranes, which limits the conclusions that can be drawn as to the definition of appropriate feedwater quality targets.

In conclusion, though biological and organic fouling issues would be expected to be more likely in SWRO and scaling in BWRO, all types of fouling can occur in both types of desalination plants. To minimize fouling potential of RO membrane systems, a high attention should be given to the design of the RO pre-treatment processes.

3. RO feedwater pre-treatment

Pretreatment of RO feedwater is a critical aspect of RO desalination as evidenced by the number of studies in the literature [12]. Traditionally, the pre-treatment system of an RO system is primarily designed to reduce the SDI of the RO feedwater to within the guideline limits. Over the years, more water quality parameters and alternative indices have been added to the guideline to address other potential challenges not covered by SDI (Table).

Cartridge filtration (CF) is present in almost all designs of RO plants, with the exception of direct UF feed of RO. CF is mostly considered as a protective unit for the RO unit more than a pre-treatment unit itself.

Fig. 2. Feedwater sources and production capacities of desalination plants (thermal and membrane-based, online and under construction in 2024) in different geographic locations (updated from [3]) with information from [2]).

Additional pre-treatment steps are usually installed upstream of the CF based on the fouling and scaling potential of the feedwater. For instance, an open intake feedwater source (e.g., surface water) or wastewater effluent typically has a higher SDI than ground water or subsurface intake sources, likely requiring more complex and advanced pre-treatment. Fig. 4 shows an overview of various pre-treatment options that can be found currently applied in SWRO and BWRO desalination plants, separated in different treatment lines depending on type of SWRO pre-treatment (with/without ultrafiltration) and the type of water source.

Particulate and colloidal fouling in RO are generally controlled by pre-treating the feedwater through granular media and/or membrane filtration. Inorganic fouling and scaling are generally addressed by conditioning of the RO feedwater through pH adjustment and/or antiscalant dosing. Organic fouling is usually minimized by coagulation-flocculation followed by a filtration, a sedimentation, or a flotation process. Biological fouling can be controlled through pre-treatment removal of organics and other nutrients through coagulation-filtration processes. Some plants may also try and address this issue through addition of chlorine or biocides as pre-treatment of the feedwater, but literature tends to highlight that this practice might turn counter-productive by producing bio-available nutrients and increasing biofouling potential [32,33]. Shock chlorination for intake pipe cleaning can be applied without the same prolonged effect. Though it can be noted that this strategy is generally designed to prevent biofouling of the plant's intake rather than of the membranes. A more extensive list of pre-treatment technologies to mitigate scaling and specific types of fouling is shown in Table 2.

Although majority of desalination plants around the world

implemented adequate pretreatment systems to produce RO feedwater quality that meets the standard industry guideline, several types of fouling and scaling are still being observed in these plants. Therefore, it is recommended that further work on these guidelines be completed as issues that are expected to be under control, such as particulate matter fouling through SDI control, still appear to occur frequently. Other fouling issues, such as biofouling for example, would require their own guidelines to limit their impact. Reviewing the guidelines for organic water quality, which can be overlooked as a precursor to biofouling [34,35], could also be an avenue for progress. Furthermore, development of new indices and/or parameters would be beneficial for the industry as highlighted by the frequent occurrence of operational issues that do not seem to be fully taken into account by those available today [36]. The following section discusses the tools available to evaluate the various fouling risks.

4. Available tools for process and water quality monitoring

The following sections detail the tools available to monitor the onset of fouling in RO plants. The first section focuses on the operational parameters that can be monitored directly on the RO unit itself and how to interpret them. The next sections 3.2–3.7 focus on each type of fouling and the analytical measurement that can be implement on the resource, throughout the treatment line or on the RO feedwater to evaluate the potential of the water to produce each specific fouling type.

4.1. Operational parameters to monitor fouling

RO plants are usually equipped with digital flow, pressure,

Fig. 3. Feedwater types of top 20 RO plants based on production capacity per awarding year since 1970. Figure created with information from [2].

Table 1
Review of autopsies from full-scale seawater and brackish water RO plants including feedwater quality.

Description	Reference	Turbidity NTU	SDI %/min	Iron total mg/L	Aluminium mg/L	Manganese mg/L	TOC mg/ L	AOC µg/ L	Fouling observed (% by mass)
Guideline		<1	<5	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05	<3	<10	
(a) Seawater									
Thirteen countries 99 modules	[18]	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	Biofouling 27 %, Oxidation 18 %, Metal oxides 12 %, Abrasion 11 %, Clay 10 %, Inorganic 8 %, Clean 10 %
Global 500 SWRO and BWRO modules	[19]	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	Biofilm/organic matter (40.5 %), Colloidal matter (38 %), metals (20.3 %), other organics (15.2 %)
Egypt, Africa Coastal wells	[20]	0.4	2.8	0.09	0.06	–	2.5	19.1	75 % inorganic 21 % organic
Busan, Korea, Asia Offshore	[21]	–	–	0.2	0.047	0.003	0.86	–	73 % inorganic (72 % Ca, 22 % Mg) 27 % organic (TOC)
Saudi Arabia, Middle East	[17]	0.2–4.4	–	0.01–0.8	1	2	–	–	Biofouling, organic fouling, inorganic fouling (iron)
(b) Brackish water									
Global 500 SWRO and BWRO modules	[19]	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	Biofilm/organic (26.3 %), colloidal (24.8 %), scale (21.4 %), metals (5.6 %)
Korea, Asia Well water	[22]	0.08	–	0.001	0.004	–	1.49	–	80 % organic, 20 % inorganic 1st pass 99 % organic second pass
Hopetoun, Australia, Oceania Surface water	[23]	0.5	–	<0.02	–	0.004	12	–	Inorganic bottom layer with top layer of proteinaceous material with Aluminium silicate crystals
Tauzhou, Zhejiang, China, Asia Water reuse	[24]	–	–	0.11	0.25	–	–	–	Biofouling and iron (36 % inorganic, 64 % organic)
Tauzhou, Zhejiang, China, Asia Surface water	[24]	–	–	0.03	0.12	–	–	–	Organic and colloidal fouling (67 % inorganic, 33 % organic)
Chile, South America Sources with high organic load	[25]	–	–	0.1	–	–	–	–	Inorganic (76 %) Organic (24 %)
Canary Island, Spain, Europe Groundwater well	[26]	–	2.2–2.7	–	–	–	–	–	Biofilm (diatoms), Inorganic scale (calcium carbonate, aluminosilicates)

temperature, and conductivity sensors, which can log data in real-time, mainly to control operation but also to monitor system integrity and fouling development. RO suppliers recommend some key parameters to monitor fouling based on sensor data and set some limits for these parameters. If at least one of these limits is exceeded, the operator needs to perform chemical cleaning on the RO and in some cases implement improvements in the pretreatment process. Prolonging the operation of the RO unit beyond these limits will put it at risk of chemically irreversible fouling, membrane damage and unacceptable product water quality. The three common parameters used in practice for both BWRO and SWRO and their guideline limits are shown in Table 3.

An alternative to normalised permeate flow is normalised permeability which is calculated as membrane flux over the normalised net driving pressure (NDP). Normalised NDP is the pressure difference between the feed-concentrate stream and the permeate stream but taking out the impact of osmotic pressure and corrected for the effect of change in water temperature.

Normalisation of operational parameters against reference conditions is necessary for fouling monitoring due to their sensitivity to changes in temperature, feed salinity (osmotic pressure), pressure or flow. For instance, a decrease in water temperature may decrease permeate flow without additional hydraulic resistance incurred from fouling. Hence, it is important to normalize these parameters to standard/reference operating conditions to measure the real impact of fouling or scaling. Major RO suppliers offer computer programs to perform normalisation of plant data without going through complicated calculations.

The feedwater source and extent of pretreatment usually give the

first indication of operational issues expected in the RO plant. Membrane autopsies (Section 2) have shown that seawater is more prone to biofouling than brackish ground water while the latter is more prone to mineral scaling than the former. Analyzing the extent of change of the specific operational parameters may further reveal symptoms of the type of fouling or issues the RO unit is experiencing as shown in Table 4. However, some types of fouling can have similar profiles and would require further investigations to identify the real cause of fouling and to plan mitigation measures. In some cases, the problem can be quite localised within the RO system so it can be useful to install sensors and monitor fouling for different stages in the RO plant. If fouling is observed mainly in the first stage, it is likely to be particulate fouling or early-stage biofouling, while if fouling is mainly observed in the last stage, it is an indication of scaling.

4.2. Biofouling

Biofouling is the result of the presence and continued growth of microorganisms on the surface of RO membranes and across the feed spacers. Several studies have focused on biofouling trying to understand its mechanisms as well as mitigating its impact on process performance. Evaluating the risk of initiation of biofouling for such processes is complex and several tools have been developed to evaluate water quality parameters that might trigger the phenomena. It is agreed upon in the literature that for biological fouling to occur the following three elements must be present: bacteria, nutrients and oxygen. Other parameters, such as temperature, cross-flow, transmembrane pressure in the RO system, etc., can have an effect on biofilm growth both in

Fig. 4. Simplified schemes of common pre-treatment options applied for RO desalination. Adapted from [30,31]. SM = sedimentation, FLC = flocculation, DAF = dissolved air flotation, PF = pressurised filter, GF = gravity filter, CF = cartridge filter, UF/MF = ultrafiltration / microfiltration.

Table 2

Overview of RO feedwater pre-treatment options and their target operational issues in brackish water (BW) and seawater (SW) RO systems.

Pre-treatment	Particulate/ colloidal	Inorganic	Scaling	Organic	Biofouling
Coagulation-flocculation	BW/SW	BW/SW		BW/SW	BW/SW
Inline coagulation	BW/SW	BW/SW		BW/SW	
Chlorination-dechlorination					BW/SW
Dissolved air flotation	BW/SW			BW/SW	
Sedimentation	BW/SW				
Sand/Multi-media filtration	BW/SW	BW/SW		BW/SW	BW/SW
Activated carbon filtration				BW	BW
Microfiltration/Ultrafiltration	BW/SW			BW/SW	BW/SW
Ion exchange softening			BW		
Lime softening		BW	BW		
pH adjustment		BW/SW	BW/SW		
Antiscalant/Scale inhibitor		BW/SW	BW/SW		
Non-oxidizing biocide dosing					BW/SW
Cartridge filtration	BW/SW				

quantity and quality [37]. Plants treating surface waters (sea, rivers, lakes) are generally more at risk of biological growth due to more elevated presence of nutrients, bacteria and overall impact from climate. Brackish water sources, often underground, are generally viewed as less vulnerable to this issue.

4.2.1. Presence of microorganisms

Bacterial quantifications are needed not only to monitor bacterial concentration in the RO feed water and along the pre-treatment but also to quantify biomass on membrane surface. Heterotrophic plate count (HPC) and total direct count (TDC) by microscope are the most common conventional bacterial quantification methods. However, they are laborious, time consuming and limited to the enumeration of cultivable bacteria [38]. Recently, new methods were employed to detect bacterial

concentration such as adenosine triphosphate (ATP) measurement and flow cytometry (FCM). These methods are fast, accurate, able to detect cultivable and non-cultivable bacteria, and can differentiate between live and dead cells. ATP is the energy source of cells including bacteria and is directly related to the activity of biomass. FCM is technique of quantitative single cell analysis by counting and examining microscopic particles using bacterial DNA staining. The limit of detection of monitoring ATP and FCM are as low as 0.1 ng-ATP/L [39] and 1000 cells/mL [40], respectively. In RO membrane applications, FCM and ATP have been used to monitor microbial potential along the RO pre-treatment and in the RO feed water of freshwater and seawater RO system [41,42], using direct addition of Promega WaterGlo reagents to water sample or by using pre-filtration step (filtration method) [43,44].

Planktonic algae, particularly micro-algae, are ubiquitous in open

Table 3

Typical guideline limits for RO (BWRO and SWRO) fouling based on operational parameters.

Parameter	Description	Guideline limits*
Normalised permeate flow	Permeate flow at current operating conditions corrected for temperature effects and normalised to standard/reference operating condition.	↓ 10 %
Normalised salt passage	Relative percentage of normalised salt concentration in the permeate stream against the average salt concentration in the feed-concentrate stream. Salt concentration in the permeate stream is normalised to standard/reference operating condition.	↑ 5–10 %
Normalised differential pressure	Difference in pressure between the inlet and outlet of the RO train at current operating conditions, normalised to standard/reference operating condition (e.g., flow and temperature).	↑ 10–15 %

* Percentage change in current value relative to the value for initially clean membrane.

Table 4

Expected impact of operational issues on the temporal changes of specific operational parameters. As more quantitative information is still not widely reported, arrows only show indicative trends of changes based on available literature and practice. Legend: ↑ increase, ↓ decrease, ↔ minimal/no change. (Source: [90]).

RO operational issues	Typical feed water sources of affected RO plants	Permeate flow	Salt passage	Differential pressure
Colloidal/particulate fouling	wastewater, river water, seawater	↓↓	↑	↑
Metal oxides fouling	groundwater, wastewater	↓↓	↑	↑
Mineral scaling	groundwater, wastewater, brine	↓↓	↑	↑
Organic fouling	Wastewater, river water, seawater	↓↓	↔	↔
Biological fouling	Wastewater, river water, seawater	↓	↔	↑↑
Oxidation damage	Chlorinated tap water or wastewater	↑	↑↑	↔
Membrane/O-ring leaks	all sources	↑	↑↑	↔

water sources. An increase in algal concentration is an indication of an algal bloom, a seasonal occurrence which can generate significant concentrations of particulate and organic foulants. Monitoring of algal cell density can be done through microscopic counting. Indirect measurement using a bulk parameter, chlorophyll-a, has also been routinely applied using standard methods [45–47]. Particulate, organic, and organic fouling can be expected during algal blooms due to the high density of algal cells and the extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) they release. Nevertheless, a very high increase in algae density or chlorophyll-a concentrations in the source water may not necessarily result in very high RO fouling because algal species causing blooms can have different cell characteristics, amount of chlorophyll-a in their cells, capacity to produce TEP/EPS (see section 4.7) and other conditions that can affect their removal through the RO pre-treatment processes [48,49]. In general, algae monitoring can be used as an early warning for the operator to increase monitoring and make necessary adjustments in the pretreatment system to minimize direct (particulate/organic fouling) or indirect (biological fouling) impact of algal blooms on RO performance.

4.2.2. Nutrients

4.2.2.1. Phosphorus. The presence of nutrients: carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus is often discussed in the form of their mass ratio as C:N:P with a ratio of 100:23:4.3 often referenced as a requirement for biological growth [50]. This ratio highlights that phosphorus is likely to be the most interesting nutrient to target for biofouling limitation [4,51–54] with concentrations below 0.3 µg PO₄⁻P/L showing promise for biofouling mitigation even in the presence of other nutrients [55]. This, however, also requires having extremely low-level of detection analytical tools in order to monitor this parameter in the feedwaters of RO units. Methods exist for this purpose [56] and have been applied for water analysis by adding a molybdate reagent and ascorbic acid to water sample at a temperature of 37 °C, forming a phosphor-molybdate complex in the acidic environment (a blue coloured complex), which is measured at 880 nm wavelength using spectrophotometer [39,57]. Monitoring of this parameter has been applied offline in full-scale desalination plants [39]. It must be noted, concerning phosphorus, that several studies have highlighted the risk of using phosphate-based antiscalants, injected ahead of RO membranes to prevent scaling, as they can increase the presence of phosphorus and thus promote biofouling [58–61].

4.2.2.2. Carbon. Carbon is the most prevalent nutrient in water systems in terms of concentration and as such is the most difficult to control. However, not all carbon is readily available as substrate for biological activity. Several methods have therefore been developed to evaluate the amount of carbon present in a water sample that can be consumed by the bacteria present. A first approach is to evaluate biodegradable dissolved organic carbon (BDOC) which is measured by evaluating dissolved organic carbon (DOC) before and after an incubation test which can be modified depending on application [62–65]. BDOC has a limit of detection around 0.1–0.2 mg/L and is often found to represent 10 to 30 % of the overall water organic carbon content. However, its main limitation for routine application is the long incubation period that can last several weeks.

Another approach to evaluate the bioavailable carbon is the AOC method which was initially developed for drinking water network water quality evaluation and has recently been adapted to seawater. The method uses the inoculation of a water sample with a specific single strain of bacteria and the subsequent monitoring of its growth. The method has been developed to evaluate various strains and inoculation times allowing to lower the limit of detection to below 10 µg-C/L and the duration of the test to 2 days [66,67]. A study by [68] has found good correlations between AOC measurement and RO fouling which highlights the interest of the method. Furthermore, studies have also shown that AOC compounds can transfer through membranes while BDOC is retained [69,70], underlining the usefulness of the method for membrane-based applications. The limitation of the method lies in the use of a single strain of bacteria which, while allowing for a standardized method, might under-evaluate the biological growth upwards of 80 % compared to the local bacterial ecosystem [71].

To overcome this potential limitation, a new method called the biological growth potential (BGP) was developed on the same basis as AOC by using indigenous inoculum with a concentration of 10,000 intact cells. The growth of the indigenous bacteria is monitored based on ATP method over 5 days of [72,73]. Development of the method has led to a 10 µg-C/L limit of detection. The use of this method on full-scale plants has shown promise in linking this analytical approach to RO pressure drop and CIP cleaning frequency. In these studies, a value of 70 µg-C/L was defined as a desirable target for biofouling limitation in SWRO plants [3,5,39,72–75].

Overall, these methods tend to be quite complex to set up and required technically skilled lab technicians to complete. Though their duration requires several days, considering that biofilms are considered

to develop in around two weeks [76], there is still value in their application as a tool for full-scale plants and at the very least for research and innovation studies.

4.2.2.3. Nitrogen. Along with phosphorus and carbon, nitrogen is important to support biological growth. The removal of bioavailable nitrogen compounds, such as ammonia, ammonium, nitrate, and nitrite in water/wastewater, have been widely explored, but not related to control biofouling in RO system. The strategy to restrict biological growth discussed in studies on biofouling in RO system mostly focused on carbon and phosphorus limitation. Due to the mass ratio of C:N:P, organic carbon is considered as the controlling factor in microbial growth [77,78] and in some cases, phosphorus can be the limiting nutrient [79–82]. Minor changes in phosphorus concentration affect biological growth significantly, while nitrogen showed negligible effects [79]. Nitrogen might be viewed as less significant in biofouling control compared to carbon and phosphorus, however, analyzing nitrogen compounds is useful for interpreting water quality data related to possible microbial growth in RO feed water. The methods used to measure nitrogenous compounds in water are available in [83,84]. Organic nitrogen concentration can also be semi-quantified using liquid chromatographic technique [85].

4.2.3. Other parameters

Water temperature affects not only biological growth but also on microbial population, bacterial cell attachment, EPS production and biofilm structure [86,87]. Biofouling due to increased microbial activity most likely to be expected during summer and of an abundance of organics in the RO feed water. The study by [87] showed that in RO systems, feed water temperature strongly influences the thickness, structure and quantity of biofouling layer. The higher temperature of feed water led to faster biofilm formation and faster pressure drop, which therefore compressed biofilm layer (decreased thickness). Moreover, at higher feed water temperature, the RO water flux is also increased leading to higher concentration polarization at the membrane surface which negatively affects the biofilm formation layer. At the end, this results in a dense, strong and compacted biofilm layer on membrane surface that is difficult to be cleaned at normal ambient temperature.

Another parameter that influences the biofilm formation on RO membrane is the dissolved oxygen concentration in the RO feed water. Biofilm formation layer usually depends on the type of bacteria present in the feed water. Aerobic bacteria are existing in warm, shallow and sunlit surface water with dissolved oxygen while anaerobic bacteria are usually existing in closed water systems with little to no dissolved oxygen and may be triggered if sufficient nutrients are introduced [88]. Both types of bacteria could potentially be present in various RO feed-water sources [89].

4.3. Oxidation

Oxidative agents, such as chlorine, are commonly used in water treatment to control biofouling in RO system. However, polyamide layer in RO membrane is prone to oxidation, leading to membrane degradation and loss in performance. In the situation where chlorine is used, the chemical reactions of chlorine and polyamides occur as N-chlorination followed by ring chlorination [90,91]. The technical manual for FilmTec RO membranes [92] mentioned that membrane degradation can occur after 200–1000 ppm.h exposure to free chlorine. To protect the membrane from residual chlorine, membrane manufacturers recommend the use of activated carbon filtration, the addition of sodium metabisulfite (SMBS) or ultraviolet pretreatment [93]. The absence of chlorine after the mixing line is indicated by oxidation-reduction potential (ORP) measurement which is the ability of a solution to either gain or lose electrons to act as an oxidizing or reducing agent. ORP is measured in millivolts (mV) and the typical threshold values applied to avoid RO

oxidation is 175–200 mV. The irreversible damage caused by oxidation is typically characterised by increasing salt passage and permeate flux.

Other disinfectant agents, such as non-oxidizing monochloramine can be considered as polyamide membranes can withstand 300,000 ppm.h chloramine exposure [94]. Shock treatment using sodium bisulfite and intermittent dosing of DBNPA (2,2, dibromo-3-nitrilopropionamide) are probably preferable as these biocides are compatible with RO membranes.

4.4. Metal oxides

The presence of metals and metal oxides can be quite detrimental to membrane through their deposition on the membrane surface. Metals such as iron, manganese and aluminium can be present naturally in the feedwater, originating for example from the surrounding geological components. However, iron and aluminium can also find their source in their use for coagulation or flotation pre-treatment units. It is therefore critical for RO operations to both (1) properly assess the source water quality and apply the proper pre-treatments in case of presence of these compounds in the water and (2) to ensure proper operations of coagulation or flotation equipment to limit residuals in the RO feedwater.

Despite known efficient pre-treatments (aeration, oxidation, filtration) and available analytical methods both in the laboratory (ICP-MS, SEM-EDX) and in the field (spectroscopy), metal oxides still represent an issue for the membranes and should not be overlooked. Membrane manufacturers, well aware of the negative impact of these elements on membranes, provide water quality guidelines for compatibility with their products.

4.5. Abrasion and particulate fouling

Abrasion of RO membranes is a major risk for RO units which operate at elevated pressures (50 to 70 bars in seawater applications). Damage can occur from feed spacer pressing into the membranes as a result of excessive fouling or the presence of particles that were not removed through the pre-treatment units. The particles can originate from the water source, from the filter media or from the corrosion of plant equipment in contact with the water. Damage such as this can result in an increase in salt passage and thus a lower quality permeate as well as increased flow rates.

Colloidal and particulate matter could be composed of clay, organics such as natural organic matter (e.g., biopolymers), metal inorganics such as aluminium and iron silicates, algae, bacteria (as individual) and exopolymer substances including transparent exopolymer particles (TEP). Flocs originated from coagulation process can also be considered as particles. These particles may contribute to the membrane fouling development and thus targeted by pre-treatment in front of RO.

There are two approaches for evaluating the risk of particulate fouling in RO treatment lines. The first is to monitor water quality using online probes to measure turbidity and/or particle counters. This is a standard practice expected to be implemented on any RO plant. The second approach has been the development of analytical procedures that allow to calculate specific indices linked to membrane fouling (Fig. 5).

The most widely applied index is the silt density index (SDI; [95]). The SDI is measured by monitoring the time taken to filter a given volume of water over time at a constant given pressure [96]. This is a simple test which requires low-cost consumables and has also been transposed to online measurement (e.g., Mabat systems) which limits the risk of operator-dependent biases. Its industry-wide acceptance is quite valuable though limitations to this approach have been well-documented [97–102]. The main issues highlighted in these studies is its limited relationship to the concentration of colloidal and suspended matter, lack of correction for temperature, lack of identification of a fouling mechanism, influence of filter properties in the measurement, influence of filter holder in the measurement, and not considering particles smaller than 0.45 μm .

Fig. 5. Historical development of fouling indices for particulate fouling assessment (adapted from [3]). Legend: FI = fouling index, SDI = silt density index, MFI = modified fouling index, MFI-UF = modified fouling index ultrafiltration, CF = constant flux, HF = Hollow fibre, ASTM = American society for testing and materials.

Several indices have since been developed to improve upon the SDI, including the modified fouling index (MFI-0.45; [103,104]) and its subsequent evolution the MFI-UF [102,104–106]. The MFI was designed to improve upon the limitations of the SDI, and evolved from a constant pressure test to a constant flux test to be able to predict the rate of fouling of RO membrane processes. The MFI-UF was further developed to use ultrafiltration membranes, thus integrating the impact of smaller particles on fouling. In addition, the MFI-0.45 and MFI-UF tests can be used to optimize pre-treatment and as a water quality indicator for infiltration in wells [107] and for RO feedwater [104,106,108,109]. The experimental materials and methods, procedures and applications were reported in detail in recent literature [96,110,111]. These indices require further data consolidation and wider use to further cement their promising results.

4.6. Mineral scaling

Mineral scaling is the result of precipitation of sparingly soluble salts as it reach supersaturation usually in the concentrate stream of the RO membrane unit. The resulting scale is dependent on water ionic composition, temperature and pH. The main scales found in RO units are calcium carbonate, calcium sulphate, calcium phosphate, barium sulphate, and silica/metal silicates. Control of scaling issues is generally completed through tuning of RO recovery, pH adjustment and/or antiscalant dosing [112–114]. It can be noted that depending on water quality, scaling control might not be needed as observed at a North Sea RO plant where operation without antiscalant was stable [115,116]. Other studies suggest a process-based approach through ion exchange or lime softening as pre-treatment ahead of the RO unit [117,118]. Scaling risk in a given water is evaluated through a variety of standard indices (saturation index, Langelier index, etc.) while in practice, design and definition of treatment lines that can limit or eliminate scaling risk are typically done using software provided by chemical suppliers and membrane manufacturers such as WAVE (DuPont), IMSDesign (Hydranautics), Membrane Master MM5 (Genesys International). Another approach to understanding scaling kinetics is the evaluation of induction time, defined as the time required for a supersaturated solution to develop nuclei at a critical size for scaling development [119–121]. A long induction time thus limits the risk of scaling [121–123] and can be monitored through changes in pH, turbidity, conductivity and given ions concentration [115,124]. This parameter still needs further development, in particular, to establish a target threshold value. The experimental procedure for performing induction time tests and a proposal of a new set-up for assessing scaling based on once-through RO filtration has been reported recently [125].

4.7. Organic fouling

As presented in Section 2, organic fouling is rarely considered an issue for process performance directly. Though it can directly cause

severe issues and decline in performance (permeability drop), it is its indirect consequence of serving as substrate, in the form of bioavailable nutrients for biological growth, that appears to be mainly reported and has been discussed previously (section 3.2.2). Natural organic matter (NOM) in environmental processes have been a subject of focus in the drinking water scientific community as understanding its origins and structure is expected to help promote more efficient treatment processes and cleaning strategies. The various analytical tools available today are summarized in Fig. 6.

The main parameter for assessing the presence and amount of organic material present in waters is total organic carbon (TOC). This bulk measurement only allows to estimate the quantity of NOM present and not the various forms it can be under which do not all imply the same risk for fouling, it is therefore important to further identify the type of organic matter present in the water. One such example is the potential interaction between cationic organic polymers and negatively charged antiscalants which can lead to irreversible fouling of membranes [92,126,127].

The first and easiest way to further characterize NOM is to apply optical methods such as the analysis of UV absorbance at 254 nm (UVA_{254}) which is a parameter related to the presence of aromatic organic material. The ratio between UVA_{254} and DOC, called specific UV absorbance, is a simple parameter that allows to discriminate waters between their hydrophilic (<2 mg/L/m) and hydrophobic (>4 mg/L/m) character, the latter being more amenable to conventional treatments such as coagulation [129,130]. While the presence of hydrophobic material is not recommended for membrane units [131], it has been noted that hydrophilic NOM can be even more problematic to membranes [132]. While these simple methods should be applied for water monitoring, more detailed NOM characterization techniques can be applied to assess the organic fouling potential of the waters to be treated.

A more specific NOM characterization technique using optical methods is the use of fluorescence analysis to produce a 3D excitation-emission matrix (EEM) from which various peaks and characteristic indices can be calculated [133]. These peaks and indices allow to evaluate the origins of the NOM present in the water but, like UV absorbance, limits itself to specific structures, in this case the compounds containing fluorophores (e.g., humic substances, protein) [134]. Polysaccharides, for example, do not respond analytically which is one of the reasons why F-EEM should be applied in combination with other methods.

To further fractionate and characterize organic components in the water, studies involving NOM analysis in water often apply Liquid chromatography-organic carbon detection (LC-OCD) which uses size exclusion chromatography in combination with three online detectors for organic carbon, UV_{254} and organic nitrogen. The resulting chromatogram shows several peaks that are broadly defined as biopolymers, humic substances, building blocks, low molecular weight acids, and low molecular weight neutrals [85]. The interest in the method is its ability to characterize these fractions with a low ppb limit of detection, its

Fig. 6. Overview of the different fractions of organic matter in the water and the applicable analytical methods to identify or quantify them [128]. LC-OCD-UVD-OND is liquid chromatography (LC) with inline detectors for organic carbon (OCD), UV absorbance at 254 nm (UVD) and organic nitrogen (OND); FEEM is fluorescence excitation-emission matrices; TEP refers to transparent exopolymer particles measured with a 0.4 μm or 10 kDa membrane.

Table 5
Parameters and recommended guideline values for RO feed water.

Parameter	Unit	RO Manufacturers	Other sources	Standard Methods
(a) Particulate fouling indicators				
SDI ₁₅	%/min	<5 (target <3)	<5 (target <3) [159] < 3 [160] < 4 [4]	[95]
MFI-0.45	s/L ²	4 (target <1)		[103]
MFI-UF	s/L ²	-	<490 at 15 lmh (safe MFI*) [104,110]	
Turbidity	NTU	< 1	< 0.5 [160] < 0.1 [4]	[163]
(b) Organic fouling indicators				
Oil and grease	mg/L	0.1	< 0.1 [160] < 0.02 [4]	[153]
TOC	mg-C/L	3	< 2 [160] < 2 (target <0.5) [4]	[164]
SUVA	L/mg-m		< 4	[131]
COD	mg/L	10		[165]
(c) Biological fouling indicators				
AOC	μg/L Ac-C	10 (target <5)	<10 (threshold for biofouling in freshwater) [161,162] [68]	[166]
BGP	μg-C/L	<50	<70 [72]	
BFR	pg-ATP/cm ²	-	< 1 [162]	
PO ₄ -P	μg/L	5 (target <1)	0.3 [55]	
(d) Inorganic fouling and scaling indicators				
Ferrous iron	mg/L	4	< 2 [160] < 2 [4]	[167]
Ferric iron	mg/L	0.05	< 0.1 [160] <0.05 [4]	[167]
Manganese	mg/L	0.05	0.05 [161] 0.02 [4]	[168]
Aluminium	mg/L	0.05		[169]
Silica	mg/L		20 [160]	[170]
pH	-		4-11 [4]	[171]
LSI (freshwater)	-	Concentrate LSI < 0 (if no antiscalant is added)		[172]
S&DSI (seawater)	-	Concentrate S&DSI < 0 (if no antiscalant is added)		[173]
(e) Membrane material limits				
Temperature	°C		< 35 [4]	
Free chlorine	mg/L	<0.1	< 0.1 [160] < 0.01 [4]	[174]
ORP	mV	<175-200		[175]

* Safe MFI is a theoretical value for RO feedwater that will yield a 1 bar pressure increase in a 6-month period.

flexibility to be implemented on highly saline waters [132] as well as its growing library of available data for comparison [35,133–143].

One specific family of organic compounds that have been linked to issues of fouling, and biological fouling in membrane processes are transparent exopolymer particles (TEP) [128,144–146]. TEP are compounds that are produced by algae and bacteria and their presence has been linked to biofilm formation. There are various methods used to assess TEP presence and concentrations in water, but their implementation can be quite complex and time-intensive and that knowledge of their limitations should be understood when interpreting data [146–149].

Finally, the organic compounds most easily defined and known to be a major issue for membrane systems are oily compounds which have standardized analytical methods [150–154]. These compounds can be of natural origin such as the presence of geological pockets of tar oil or come from human activity pollution such as discharge from seafaring vessels. These should be routinely monitored to ensure safe operations.

5. RO feedwater guidelines and full-scale RO feedwater qualities

RO feedwater guidelines available from both manufacturers [92,155,156] and the scientific literature are presented in Table 5. Manufacturers focus on standardized methods with a particular attention given to the SDI, though [157] recently included the MFI-0.45 [158] to their list. Scientific literature offers a focus on more complex parameters, which, while not routine, have for objective to find parameters that will allow to further minimize the issues still facing RO units as highlighted in section 2.

A review of available literature on SWRO and BWRO feedwater quality was conducted to evaluate the ability of RO plants to meet these industry guidelines. The initial result highlighted by this search is the limited availability of such data. Very few papers have focused on this type of data and showed a wide range of water quality parameters in full-scale plants and/or in the feedwater of RO units. More extensive data is expected to be found in specialized desalination conference

proceedings (e.g., IDRA, EDS) where plant operators often present operational case studies. Consolidating that data would require a very time-intensive but valuable step. Despite these limitations, the data presented in Table 6 is expected to be representative of full-scale RO plants.

Data obtained showed that RO plants usually are efficient at keeping water quality below the required guidelines for particulate fouling (i.e., SDI and turbidity) which is the main issue suppliers are the most stringent about. Data corresponding to organic and biological fouling parameters were not always below the suggested guidelines however, indicating that such issues are not as well controlled.

Despite industry guidelines to limit the presence of oxidative and inorganic compounds, it appears that either those guidelines are not matched or are not stringent enough. Very little data on these compounds were found, though it should be noted that a study [196] measured dissolved and total Al, Fe and Si and found that while the dissolved forms were well below the guideline thresholds, the total values exceeded those for Al and Fe. This could be an explanation as to why inorganic fouling is often found as an issue despite stringent standards. These metals have rather low solubility in water, so guideline concentration limits tend to be low as well. In practice, RO feedwater concentration, though remaining low, tends to exceed guideline limits. Accumulation in RO might be a slow process with an impact only obvious after long term operations.

Overall, publication of full-scale plant water quality, throughout the treatment line, would be a valuable addition to the scientific literature. Data for parameters that do not correspond to the main industrial guidelines would be quite welcome to evaluate organic and biological fouling risks. BWRO studies tend to focus only on TDS and ion composition of the resource, likely due to scaling being a more important issue than particulate fouling for groundwater resources.

Finally, despite available guidelines and mostly good quality waters in terms of particulate issues specifically, there are still numerous operational issues involving fouling of different sorts as evidenced by the review of published autopsies. This highlights the need to further

Table 6
Water quality in SWRO and BWRO feedwater respective to industry guidelines/recommendations.

Parameter	Unit	Source water		RO feedwater guideline/ recommended limits	References
		Seawater	Brackish water ^a		
(a) Particulate fouling indicators					
SDI ₁₅	%/min	0.5–4.9	<1–3.3	<5 (target <3)	[101,108,175–187]
MFI	s/L ²	0.31–2.1	≤0.1–0.5		[132,176,185,188]
MFI-UF	s/L ²	125–16,000	740–22,600	–	[49,104,106,185,187,189]
Turbidity	NTU	0.1–5.5	0.4	< 1	[177,180,181,183,184,190]
(b) Organic fouling indicators					
TOC/DOC	mg-C/L	0.7–6	1.5–10	< 3	[39,49,67,181,188,190–194]
UV ₂₅₄	1/m	0.7–13	–	< 12 ^b	[177,181,184,191,194]
SUVA	L/mg.m	0.7–1.14	3.03		[132,184,194]
TEP _{0.4µm}	µg XG/L	10–740	10–110	–	[34,49,190,195]
Chlorophyll-a	mg/m ³	0.02–60	<2–18	–	[34,49]
(c) Biological fouling indicators					
AOC	µg/L Ac-C	<10–130	–	10 (target <5)	[67,140,184]
BGP	µg-C/L	90–190	–	–	[39,43,74,197]
PO ₄ -P	µg/L	11.8–160	<50–1200	< 0.3	[184,190]
ATP	µg/L	16–19	–	–	[39,43,196,197]
Total cell count	cells/mL	118–1,200,000	–	–	[181,187,190–192,195]
(d) Inorganic fouling and scaling indicators					
Ferric iron	mg/L	<0.02	ND - 0.15	< 0.05	[180,186,194,196]
Manganese	mg/L	<0.01	< 0.01–0.5	< 0.05	[180,186,194,196]
Aluminium	mg/L	<0.01 (0.4)	ND - 0.15	< 0.05	[176,186,194,196]
Silica	mg/L	0.04–8 (1.1)	1.5–25	< 20	[176,180,186,196]
pH	–	8.1	6–8.2	4–11	[176,180,186]

^a excluding wastewater.

^b calculated from TOC and SUVA guidelines.

study these issues and understand the phenomena behind fouling occurrence, water quality targets and pre-treatment operations.

6. Outlook and opportunities

Due to expected increase in water scarcity in various regions of the world, the application of RO-based desalination of brackish and saline waters is projected to grow steadily. Such processes are sensitive to feedwater quality and the risk of fouling needs to be managed properly to mitigate any risks to the membranes. However, as evidenced in this review, the existing guidelines and analytical tools appear to not be sufficient for proper control and monitoring of these issues.

The development of new methods for both water quality analysis and operations control appears to be required for every type of fouling issues and experimental methods are available for its assessment [110]. While particulate fouling appears to be the most controlled issue, with several indices and corresponding threshold values, there still is need for a better predictive approach to ensure membranes are not at-risk during operations.

Scaling seems to be a well-understood phenomenon with salts precipitating out of solution once supersaturation is achieved. The possibility of further studying this phenomenon through induction time might be an interesting approach to further detail these mechanisms and how to control if not prevent them from occurring [122,125]. Several design tools exist to limit these issues, but development of online monitoring techniques appears to be an area for improvement that should be considered.

Organic fouling and organic matter characterization has less interest in the literature mainly due to its often being shadowed by the co-current development of biological fouling, the leading cause of RO operational issues. However, the need to understand its impact on both biological processes and membrane performance is a definite need.

Biological fouling has been the focus of several studies and though there is an agreement on how this issue appears and develops in membrane processes, there are also limited tools for predicting its potential occurrence. Analytical methods usually require several days to produce results and require extremely low detection limits to be able to assess the expected threshold values for biofouling limitation. Improving these two areas as well as advancing the understanding of the controlling parameters and development of biological growth would thus be of interest to the field. Recently, the use of genomic methods has shown potential for producing new knowledge on microbial communities, structure and interactions [192,198–200]. Ongoing research and development of these tools is expected to increase in the coming years.

Current RO feedwater quality guidelines have been very valuable for pre-treatment selection and design as well as plant operation monitoring, they have also shown limitations for full control of fouling issues. Further developments are therefore required in the ongoing effort of the industry to improve sustainable desalination practices and understanding. And though additional parameters would translate to increased need for plant operator control, it is expected this would be balanced out by a decrease in operational expenditure. A focus on onsite monitoring with low-cost consumables, standardization as well as online monitoring would prove critical for industry-wide integration.

It is suggested that publication of operational data from actual full-scale plants would be very valuable for continued study of these issues. BWRO studies, due to the nature of the treated resources, also often only produce data for inorganic components of the water while other parameters (NOM content, SDI measurements, etc.) would be valuable. Further studies of chemicals used in treatment lines and their potential impact on fouling would also provide significant knowledge for operators when needing to select the appropriate products.

It can be noted that feedwater guidelines for emerging membrane-based desalination technologies such as forward osmosis and membrane distillation are currently non-existent. Future developments of these new technologies should also include understanding their

propensity to fouling or scaling by applying current or new feedwater quality assessment methods. The development of which being likely to also benefit RO applications.

Abbreviations and symbols

AOC	Assimilable organic carbon
ATP	Adenosine tri-phosphate
BGP	Bacterial growth potential
BFR	Biofilm formation rate
BWRO	Brackish water reverse osmosis
CIP	Cleaning in place
COD	Chemical oxygen demand
DOC	Dissolved organic carbon
EEM	Excitation-emission matrix
EPS	Exo-polymer substances
ICP-MS	Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry
LC-OCD	Liquid chromatography-organic carbon detection
LoD	Limit of detection
LSI	Langelier saturation index
MED	Multi-effect distillation
MFI-0.45	Modified fouling index, constant pressure, 0.45 µm filter
MFI-UF	Modified fouling index, constant flux, 10 kDa or 100 kDa membrane filter
MSF	Multi stage flash distillation
NOM	Natural organic matter
RO	Reverse osmosis
SDI	Silt density index, %/min
S&DSI	Stiff and Davis saturation index
SEM-EDX	Scanning electron microscopy with energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy
SWRO	Seawater reverse osmosis
TEP	Transparent exopolymer particles
TOC	Total organic carbon
UV254	Ultra-violet absorbance at 254 nm

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Declaration of competing interest

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Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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